

Simple Analytical Method for Organophosphorus Pesticide Determination and its Application in Plants

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Manuscript received 12 August 1986, revised 18 November 1986, accepted 3 January 1987

A new, simple, rapid and sensitive photometric method is developed for the determination of organophosphorus pesticides in plant materials. The method involves the formation of 12-molybdophosphoric acid from orthophosphate and excess of molybdate in acid solution followed by the reduction with succinylhydrazide to give molybdenum blue. The dye extracted in n-butanol shows absorption at 780 nm. The proposed method is free from the interference of Mo, As and Cu. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity are found to be $3.75 \pm 0.05 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.008 \mu\text{g}$, respectively.

IN India, the increasing use of pesticides and insecticides in the agriculture sector and poisoning due to accidental or occupational hazards has been recognised and documented as an episode in Cochin (1955) and Sitapur-Hardoi (1977)¹. Organophosphorus compounds exhibit a wide range of toxicity to mammals. A number of incidents of accidental phosphorus poisoning have been reported²⁻⁴. Phosphorus poisoning results in constriction of pupils, blurred vision and pain behind the eyes. More severe poisoning causes drooling, sweating, nausea, involuntary defaecation or urination followed by convulsions, coma and eventual death through asphyxia^{5,6}.

The wide use of toxic organophosphorus has created a need for simple analytical methods for their determination and estimation of minute quantities of these toxic compounds in plant materials. Many photometric methods for the determination of organophosphorus pesticides have been reported in literature⁷⁻¹⁰. The molybdenum blue method is a well established method. Various reducing agents¹¹⁻¹⁴ are reported in literature, but most of them suffer from some drawback, like sensitivity, stability of colour¹⁵ interference from Cu and As, time required for full colour development and absorption by blank, etc.

In the present communication succinylhydrazide (SDH) is introduced as a reducing agent for the spectrophotometric determination of organophosphorus pesticides on the surface of plants.

Experimental

All spectrophotometric measurements were carried out in a ECIL GS 865 spectrophotometer and Carl-Zeiss spekol with 1 cm matched silica cells.

A 10 M sulphuric acid solution and a 2.5% (w/v) solution of ammonium molybdate were prepared in demineralised water. Succinylhydrazide (SDH) was prepared by adding hydrazine hydrate (0.1 mol in ethanol) to the solution of diethylsuccinate (0.05 mol in ethanol) in 2 : 1 mole ratio; the white solid obtained being recrystallised from water¹⁶. A 0.1% solution of SDH was prepared in demineralised water. A stock solution of potassium dihydrogen phosphate containing 1 mg/ml of P was prepared and the working standard was prepared by appropriate dilution of the stock solution.

The following standard solution of organophosphorus pesticides containing 1 mg/ml of P were prepared: (i) Parathion (Bayer India Ltd., 2% dust) prepared in ethanol ($\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{14}\text{NO}_5\text{PS}$, 291.3), (ii) Malathion (Cyanamid India Ltd., 50 E.C) prepared in ethanol ($\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_6\text{PS}_2$, 330.3), (iii) Quinolphos (Sandoz India Ltd., 25 E.C) prepared in ethanol ($\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_2\text{O}_6\text{PS}$, 289.3), and (iv) Monocrotophos (Ciba Giegy of India, 40 E.C) prepared in demineralised water ($\text{C}_7\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_5\text{PM}_2$, 223). Working standard were prepared by the appropriate dilution of the stock solution.

All the other chemicals used were of AnalaR grade.

Procedure: To an aliquot (~50 ml) of the pesticide sample solution containing 1-7 μg of P, was added ammonium molybdate solution (2ml) and the acidity was adjusted to ~2.2 N with 10 N H_2SO_4 . Succinylhydrazide solution (1 ml) was then added and the mixture was kept over a boiling water-bath for 2 min, allowed to cool for 10 min for full colour development and then transferred quantitatively into a separatory funnel. The blue colour was extracted with n-butanol ($2 \times 0.5 \text{ ml}$). The absorbance of blue coloured

dye was measured at 780 nm against the reagent blank. Since the absorption of reagent blank is negligible, n-butanol was taken as reference solution. The concentration of phosphorus was read out from the calibration curve. Calibration curve for standard phosphorus solution (containing 1-7 μg of phosphorus) was prepared following the above procedure.

Procedure for organophosphorus residue on plant surface: Forty-five plant samples were taken and were sprayed with different pesticides. These plant materials were placed in a funnel and washed with ethanol. Washings were collected in boiling tube and the phosphorus content analysed as described earlier. In order to check the validity of the method, it was compared with the conventional ascorbic acid method¹⁷. Results shown in Table 1 indicate that the proposed method is identical to those of the existing method.

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS OF ORGANOPHOSPHORUS PESTICIDES FROM THE SURFACE OF PLANT

Pesticides sprayed on plants	Proposed method	Conventional method*
	Pesticide found μg	Pesticide found μg
Parathion	2.10	2.05
	4.25	4.24
	1.65	1.66
Malathion	1.11	1.12
	2.90	2.93
	5.57	5.57
Quinolphos	3.85	3.85
	4.65	4.64
	5.31	5.30
Monocrotophos	6.78	6.73
	7.16	7.16
	8.15	8.16

*Ref. 14.

Results and Discussion

Effect of variables: Maximum intensity of colour was obtained in the range 2.2-2.5 M sulphuric acid when the solution was kept for 2 min on a boiling water bath and cooled for 10 min for full colour development. 2 ml of 2.5% ammonium molybdate and 1-2 ml of succinyl dihydrazide solutions were sufficient for full colour development under the conditions reported. The reproducibility of the method was checked by replicate analysis of standard phosphorus and sample solution over a period of 7 days. The tolerance limit (in 5 μg P per 50 ml) of foreign ions were as follows: Ba^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , chloride, carbonate and sulphate (100 ppm); Fe^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , As^{3+} , Mo^{IV} , Sb^{3+} , W^{VI}

and carbonate (60 ppm); Mg^{2+} , nitrate and nitrite (30 ppm); Cu^{2+} (20 ppm). Silicon which commonly interferes with the methods of phosphorus could be easily removed by extracting the phosphomolybdic acid into n-butanol and then developing the colour as silicomolybdic acid is not extracted in n butanol.

The present method is free from the interference due to Mo, As and Cu. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity¹⁸ were found to be $3.75 \pm 0.05 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0008 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$, respectively.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to the Head, Department of Chemistry, Ravishankar University, Raipur, for providing facilities. One of the authors (S.S.) is thankful to Ravishankar University for providing fellowship.

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